

Big Data Analytics for Improving supply chain transparency and efficiency

Rajesh Kotha

Senior Software engineer at Kroger

ABSTRACT

Industry 4.0 is rapidly approaching all over the world. Upcoming industrial revolutions will prioritize functions and services provided by devices that produce or store extensive information. A company's supply chain is made up of extensive information coming from production, transportation and other operations. The extensive data may be examined using big data analytics (BDA) to make inferences improve the supply chain management. BDA leads to new possibilities. Supply chain elements, including inventory forecasting and prediction, may be assessed using this data. This study examines how Big Data Analytics (BDA) can foster reliability in the supply chain. BDA adds value by enhancing automated procedures and using predictive analytical methods to provide new opportunities. Big data analytics is utilized to create an integrated, effective, and flexible supply chain in a highly competitive industry. The proliferation of data has facilitated the development of technology capable of effectively analyzing vast volumes of data.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management (SCM), Big Data Analytics (BDA), Data-Driven Decision Making, Inventory Management, Supply Chain Innovation, Competitive Advantage, Demand Forecasting, Machine Learning, Real-Time Data, Predictive Analytics.

INTRODUCTION

BDA is characterized by mobility, high diversity, and a substantial volume of information with the aim of improving internal operations and the decision-making process [6]. The availability of large amounts of data, the capacity to collect the information, and the incorporation of potent analytical tools into massive data sets have all contributed to the recent rise in the popularity of BDA. The administration of a network of upstream and downstream businesses is known as supply chain management. Information on the commodity was traditionally stored and sent via physical documents. However, the contemporary supply chain is very different.

As depicted by Figure 1, Businesses may collect, store, process, analyze, and exchange knowledge regarding their operations through BDA and a supply chain supported by a unique information flow. The contemporary supply chain links businesses to promote cooperation and integration on many levels. Big data analysis helps with information management in supply chain management by facilitating data provision and enhancing access. Companies and manufacturers are increasingly using data analytics to optimize their supply networks as digital technologies gain popularity. This movement has the potential to completely transform the logistics sector, making big data analytics a crucial tool in supply chain. BDA increases transparency and enhances real-time control regardless of the data's location.

SCOPE

Executives can utilize the study's conclusions when choosing the best BDA instruments. This study focuses on uses, effects, solutions, as well as the components of BDA. Empirical data is then reviewed to assess the relationships underlying supply chain efficiency, electronic purchasing features, and business analytics competencies. The remainder of the study is structured into a literature review on big data analytics, industrial supply chains, and sustainability. After that, the methodology, discussion, and conclusion are presented. The study validates strong and positive relationships between BDA and sustainability.

Figure 1: Data Analytics Process [2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to one research [1] there exist relationships between the supply chain's players and the chain itself. The real flow of raw materials, produced items, work-in-progress inventory, and returned items are all correlated with data and financial flow. This is possible due to the characteristics of BDA depicted in Figure 2. The contemporary globalized business environment causes difficulties when the supply chain managers try to keep track of such physical products because of their connectivity. Organizations must research cutting-edge methods and technology to get a competitive advantage in this intricate supply chain. The movement from supplier to consumer was traditionally organized in a sequential fashion. Currently, though, information does not follow a straight channel; rather, it flows concurrently through digital interactions involving all supply chain participants. Companies are learning how to leverage massive amounts of data since it is extremely difficult to organize and analyze enormous volumes of data in a way that helps the business.

Figure 2: "Characteristics of Big data analytics" [2].

"Big data has enormous benefits for supply chain management" [2]. BDA data can reduce the risk involved in paying for architecture and outside capacity that is required under the contract. The data illustrates how supplier networks grow, enter emerging markets, and develop over time. The floor administration and production logistics procedures may be streamlined by combining analytical approaches, increasing the output of new goods, and reducing logistic expenses. Big data is becoming more and more beneficial for the commerce, shipping, logistics, and industrial sectors. Also, customer viewpoints may be understood using big data analytics. Customers are happier when more specialized goods and services are developed as a result of a better understanding of their demands.

According to a study [3], BDA can help management strategies to transfer information across locations. For big data analytics to work, the data needs to be precise, up-to-date, consistent, and comprehensive. Point-of-sale data is necessary to assess the market. A GPS transponder is also required to create transportation records utilizing data analytics. Marketing has transformed customer knowledge into an adaptable system that produces massive amounts of data. Sophisticated techniques for client data analysis are needed to connect with the customer. Improved integration between consumer feedback and the supply chain management system is required. Data may be utilized to comprehend consumer information and societal behavior. According to one study [3], different data types—both structured and unstructured—might be assessed in order to lower supply chain process costs and satisfy customer requests (Figure 3). This is now possible because of supply chain innovations, increased data volume, and quicker distribution. BDA may improve different operations such as product creation and distribution optimization.

Companies use a variety of Big Data analytics techniques to get precise outcomes. Also, they use predictive analysis to assess organizational sustainability.

Figure 3: “Big data supply chain” [3].

Some studies claim that businesses utilize supply chain analytics to reduce risk and keep an eye on publicly accessible channels like social media and news, which provide a range of data types and allow users to connect that data to other sources [7]. Using this approach, businesses may take advantage of market possibilities. This approach fosters the development of a backup plan as well by regularly gathering up-to-date information on suppliers and the sourcing sector. The majority of research studies focus on developing general models or techniques to simulate supplier risk or figure out how supplier risk influences the efficiency of supply chains. Supply chain analysis is an effective technique that companies may use to evaluate, oversee, and monitor suppliers to identify more reliable sources. Supply chain analytics evaluate and analyze supplier performance quickly through accurate data collection and information aggregation from various supply chain channels. Information is also analyzed with regard to timeframes and quality delivery assurance. Supply chain analytics helps businesses make accurate decisions. With the use of technology and techniques, supply chain analytics can accurately forecast demand, enabling planning that is in line with expectations.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

BDA is used to describe data, but it deviates from the conventional database structure. Big Data is made up of several important technology categories, such as Hadoop (Figure 4) and HDF. Businesses utilize supply chain analytics to reduce risk and keep an eye on publicly accessible channels like social media and news, which provide a range of data types and allow users to connect that data to other sources. Despite this, studies depict that organizations use less than 5% of their accessible data efficiently [3]. This is because the rest is too costly to handle. Big Data comes from a variety of sources and encompasses all sorts of unstructured data sources that are expanding significantly and not only conventional relational data. For example, data generated by machines grows rapidly and has rich, varied information that must be found. Human-derived data from social media is another example, and it is more textual, but the insightful information is frequently buried behind a mountain of plausible interpretations [8]. These technologies are generally relatively inexpensive, and a large portion of the software is available under open source. Opensource software and cheap hardware are combined in Hadoop, the most widely used framework. It receives data streams and also offers tools for data analysis.

Figure 4: Data architecture with Hadoop [1].

SOLUTION

BDA is becoming more and more essential to modern enterprises in the ever-changing world of commerce. It is the basis for intelligent decision-making, and it gives enterprises the ability to access a wealth of insights. Companies that carefully examine the abundance of information found in raw data may turn it into a goldmine for strategic growth. Within the intricate and networked realm of supply chain management, data becomes the cornerstone of achievement. Data, like a skilled navigator, shows the way to operational excellence, enabling companies to coordinate the complex dance of distribution, transportation, and procurement. Supply chain businesses simplify inventory management, anticipate interruptions, and solve the mystery of changing demand by utilizing data. Data-driven supply chain companies reach new heights through these calculated moves, increasing productivity, cutting expenses, and strengthening their competitive advantage in a market that is always changing.

“Statistical algorithms, machine learning techniques, and historical data are used in predictive analytics, a data-driven methodology, to forecast future occurrences and trends”. Figure 5 shows an example of predictive analytics used in healthcare. Businesses are able to predict future results by examining historical patterns. The goal is to make proactive judgments and streamline several areas of the industry, such as supply chain demand forecasting. Because it makes it possible to estimate demand accurately and assists companies in maintaining ideal stock levels, predictive analytics is essential to inventory management. Also, predictive models may produce accurate inventory requirements for various durations by examining previous sales information, changes in the seasons, and other pertinent considerations. Thus, companies may optimize carrying costs and minimize stockouts and overstocking by modifying their inventory levels accordingly. Supply chain planning with data analytics helps lower risk by anticipating potential problems and disruptions. With the use of these insights, data-driven backup plans can be developed, strengthening and modifying the supply chain to withstand disruptions better.

Figure 5: predictive analytics in healthcare.

IMPACT

“Supply chain management is relying more and more on data analytics to provide real-time insights that improve operational efficiency”. As depicted in Figure 6, applying data-driven decision-making is important for customers, transparency, and the supply chain. It enables companies to properly estimate demand, keep an eye on inventory levels, and foresee any problems. Businesses are improving supply chain efficiency and transparency by integrating sophisticated analytics solutions, which raise customer satisfaction and reduce operating expenses. The profitability of these businesses has increased by 23%. This demonstrates how important data analytics is to improving supply chain efficiency. Furthermore, by facilitating well-informed decision-making, data analytics supports supply chain optimization. It provides practical insights into a range of supply chain topics, including demand and supply management and warehouse automation trends. This enables companies to increase customer happiness, save expenses, and streamline processes.

Figure 6: Reasons for applying data-driven decision-making.

Businesses may identify and eliminate inefficiencies and bottlenecks to optimize their processes by employing data analytics. For example, MHD Supply Chain notes that data analytics-driven warehouse automation has greatly increased processing speed and accuracy. Businesses may optimize levels of stock, save holding costs, and minimize waste by utilizing predictive data analytics. According to research, “data analytics may help supply chains save a significant amount of money by helping businesses predict demand precisely and modify inventory levels in response” [4]; (Figure 7). Managers can swiftly make well-informed decisions with the help of advanced analytics technologies, which provide actionable information. By using data analytics, companies demonstrate the value of making decisions based on facts.

Figure 7: Data-driven supply chain capabilities [4].

Businesses hoping to succeed in an increasingly competitive sector must now enforce BDA [9]. The potential for data-driven supply chains is growing as technology advances, providing improved efficiency and tactical benefits. Businesses may enhance their present operations and get ready for new possibilities and challenges in the ever-changing logistics industry by adopting these advances. This emphasizes how important data analytics is to achieving corporate success. Companies are anticipated to use more data analytics in the future greatly. Businesses should anticipate and enforce increasingly advanced analytics solutions that help them better improve their supply chains in line with ongoing technology developments. This expansion demonstrates how data analytics can help optimize processes and allow companies to keep a competitive advantage over rivals. There are significant changes in the logistics industry as a result of supply chain management optimization founded on sophisticated data analytics. This shift is giving firms more decision-making power while simultaneously increasing efficiency and cutting expenses.

USES

“Whether used in health care, government, finance, or some other industry, big data analytics is behind some of the most significant industry advancements in the world today” [2, para. 1]. Big data analytics generates insightful business information by applying sophisticated analytics to massive collections of both structured and unstructured data. BDA is extensively utilized in many different industries, including artificial intelligence, retail, medical care, higher education, insurance, and production, to determine what works and what does not to enhance systems, procedures, and profitability. It is made up of a lot of sorted and unordered data that, when analyzed, provides important information. BDA is used to accomplish this effectively and fast, allowing experts to use the data to make wise decisions. Businesses may use marketing analytics to use their data to find market segments that need greater focus and development. In the process of producing their goods and services, businesses may reduce costs and increase value for consumers by managing their data [10]. In many corporate areas, the drive for enhanced efficiency results in more intelligent actions, more revenues, and happier customers. Big data analytics provides insightful knowledge that improves society’s ability to operate. In addition to monitoring and analyzing records, the health care sector employs BDA to measure results globally. For example, the healthcare departments of many different countries across the world are able to obtain guidance on vaccines and methods that might prevent breakouts of such a pandemic in the future thanks to DBA (Figure 8).

Figure 8: “Application of big data and total reported Covid 19 cases by country” [5].

Digital consumer footprints found on search engines, social media platforms, and purchasing trends provide businesses with insights on their target audience's demands and preferred methods of service. Because of this, BDA assists companies in identifying consumer behavior so that they can cater to the unique demands of each customer. No doubt, this makes the customers very happy and loyal. By offering the most individualized shopping experience and suggestions based on past purchases and browsing activity, Amazon has taken advantage of this big data advantage. They integrate big data into their systems to enhance customer service, boost productivity and efficiency, and develop and execute marketing plans that can boost sales and enhance profit margins. Effective use of big data gives Amazon a competitive edge over businesses that have not yet adopted big data analytics (BDA) as it allows the corporation to make better choices more efficiently.

CONCLUSION

BDA is the main force behind the entire supply chain. The management can accurately assess big data after examining the procedures and actions that contribute to the creation of an effective BDA. Today, BDA has shown to have practical applications that help solve some of the most important issues confronting the supply chain. Volume, diversity, velocity, truthfulness, and value are some of these issues. Additionally, this includes intricate data from supply chain activities. The study found that the use of BDA can bring a new phenomenon that can help with managing the expanding volume of data in the supply chain infrastructure. The study also found that more experts with the required skill sets might be needed to improve the application of BDA. The use of data analytics is becoming necessary as a result of the rising complexity and intricacy of supply chain networks in the more globalized contemporary environment. Every link in the supply chain needs effective instruments and techniques for precise forecasting, which supports wise choices. Therefore, data integration technologies must remain updated to improve the accuracy and reliability of the supply chain.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Y. Yamada, Y. Shirasaki, and R. Nishi, "Nano-JASMINE and small-JASMINE data analysis," vol. 330, pp. 104–105, April, 2017, doi: 10.1017/S1743921317005269. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://iacis.org/iis/2015/2_iis_2015_81-90.pdf
- [2]. H. Patel. "What is Big Data Analytics and Why it is so Important?" May, 23, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://medium.com/@patelharshali136/what-is-big-data-analytics-and-why-it-is-so-important-1de86fa37540>
- [3]. M. Walker. "The Big Data Supply Chain and Data Science Management," Data Science Association, September, 4, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datascienceassn.org/content/big-data-supply-chain-and-data-science-management>
- [4]. W. Yu, R. Chavez, M. Jacobs & M. Feng. "Data-driven supply chain capabilities and performance: A resource-based view." *Transportation Research Part E: logistics and transportation review*, 114, 371-385. June, 17, 2018. <https://kar.kent.ac.uk/61680/1/BD%20SCC%20and%20Performance%20for%20TRE%20-%20New%20Version%20-%20Accepted%20Version.pdf>
- [5]. N. Mehta & S. Shukla. "Pandemic Analytics: How Countries are Leveraging Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence to Fight COVID-19?" Springer, November, 09, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s42979-021-00923-y>
- [6]. C. Vitari and E. Raguseo, 'Big data analytics business value and firm performance: linking with environmental context', *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 58, no. 18, pp. 5456–5476, September, 21, 2020. <https://hal.science/hal-02293765/document>
- [7]. A. Dehkhodaei, B. Amiri, H. Farsijani, and A. Raad, 'Barriers to big data analytics (BDA) implementation in manufacturing supply chains', *J. Manag. Anal.*, pp. 1–32, March, 1, 2020. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Amirhossein-Dehkhodaei/publication/368922540_Barriers_to_big_data_analytics_BDA_implementation_in_manufacturing_supply_chains/links/64a039bf95bbbe0c6e06d3aa/Barriers-to-big-data-analytics-BDA-implementation-in-manufacturing-supply-chains.pdf
- [8]. A. Mohamed, M. K. Najafabadi, Y. B. Wah, E. A. K. Zaman, and R. Maskat, 'The state of the art and taxonomy of big data analytics: view from new big data framework', *Artif. Intell. Rev.*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 989–1037, February, 1, 2020. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10462-019-09685-9>
- [9]. R. Iqbal, F. Doctor, B. More, S. Mahmud, and U. Yousuf, 'Big data analytics: Computational intelligence techniques and application areas', *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change*, vol. 153, no. 119253, p. 119253, April, 24, 2020. <https://pureportal.coventry.ac.uk/files/23233843/Binder2.pdf>
- [10]. D. Syed, A. Zainab, A. Ghrayeb, S. S. Refaat, H. Abu-Rub, and O. Bouhali, 'Smart grid big data analytics: Survey of technologies, techniques, and applications', *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 59564–59585, October, 16, 2020. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/iel7/6287639/6514899/09272794.pdf>